

THE PROBLEM OF RAPID DEVELOPMENT IN THE LITERATURE OF JAPANESE AND GULF ARAB COUNTRIES

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the issues of rapid development in Japanese and Gulf Arab literature. The late 19th and early 20th centuries played an important role in the history of Japanese literature. The 20-year period following the Mayji Revolution, which opened the door to a new era, was a time of serious change for Japanese literature. Long-term research on the further development of Japanese national literature has begun to be resolved

Writers of New Japan, who have experienced the rise and fall of the democratic movement for freedom and the rights of the people in the 1980s, have emerged in the country. The most talented of them became masters of Japanese literature of the 20th century.

The issue of synthesis of cultures has become one of the most important issues in Japanese literary consciousness. In particular, the aesthetic diversity of the West and the East has created a process of interdependence. The traditions of both cultures, due to the peculiarities of their historical development, required the mutual study of each other, which did not exist. In the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, this law was evident in Japanese literature.

Japanese literature developed during the late 19th and early 20th centuries with dramatic changes. In the post-Mayji Revolution, a close acquaintance with Western literature led to the emergence, transformation, and the emergence of a new era of Japanese literature as a result of theoretical knowledge of Japanese literature.

The formation of Arab Gulf literature took place in the second half of the twentieth century, decades after the development of modern literature in Egypt, Syria, Lebanon, Iraq, and Tunisia. By the end of the 20th century, it joined the world literary process and gained worldwide popularity.

Literary revival in Egypt, Lebanon, Syria, and some Arab Maghreb countries began in the second half of the 19th century. switched to literature.

As a result, by the late 21st century Arabic literature had a similar path to the development of advanced Arabic literature, but they were distinctive.

This situation has led to the emergence of a "theory of rapid development" in the example of late modern literature. In the Gulf Arabian Gulf, Kuwait, Bahrain, Qatar and other Arab countries have become more complex and controversial in the form of a rapid leap into, or jump to, a new type of modern literature.

However, the rapid development of literature in the Persian Gulf has not gone unnoticed either. The emergence of modern literature in Kuwait, Bahrain, Yemen, Saudi Arabia began in the 40-50's of the 20th century and quickly gained popularity in the Arab world and reached the level of Egyptian and Syrian literature. However, in Qatar, Oman and the United Arab Emirates, the process of renewal of literature began much later, in the 60-70s of the 20th century, and there was a rapid movement towards publication of literary activity in other Arab countries.

Keywords: *Japanese literature, theory of intensive development, literary trends, romanticism, realism, synthesis culture, social conditions, literature of the Arabian Gulf countries.*

INTRODUCTION

Japan, with its oriental ancient history, high culture and spiritual wealth, is among the countries that have made a significant contribution to the treasure of world literature. Kunchikar writers have been creating meaningful and high works for centuries. The perfection of its ideas,

characters, direction and artistry has made Japanese literature a force to be reckoned with in the world.

The period covering the end of the XIXth and the beginning of the XX centuries has an important place in the history of Japanese literature. The 20-year period after the Meiji Revolution, which opened the door to a new era, became a period of serious change for Japanese literature. The long-standing search for the further development of Japanese national literature has begun to find its solution¹.

In this period, the spiritual life of the nation developed, and acute questions were raised about which artistic system related to the worldview should be accepted as the most important. The process of changing the traditional views that defined the structure and order of the old literature, which began in the 70s and 80s, continued. The struggle of the new artistic consciousness and views with the old ones was decided in favor of the former.

Writers who experienced the rise and decline of the democratic movements "for freedom and people's rights" in the 80s of the XX th century, and who are considered peers of the new Japan, are beginning to appear in the country. The most talented of them became figures of Japanese literature of the XXth century.

In Japan, the formation of literature showing advanced stages of capitalism began in the 80s of the XIX century, that is, less than a hundred years later than in France or Russia. At one time, Japan's development was very rapid, and in a short period of time, Japan caught up with countries that had recently surpassed it in some areas, mainly in capitalist development. This led to the continuation of certain stages in the development of Japanese literature for a very short period of time. While Romanticism lasted for several decades in Europe, this trend lasted only one decade (90s) in Japan. This situation has always led to the incorrectness of these stages, to the underdevelopment of the elements that make up and are characteristic of them. One direction did not develop fully and gave way to another².

MAIN PART. The old literary schools and movements, which did not reflect the serious shifts that occurred in the entire system of artistic thought, were poured without arousing any interest. In the literary field, the representatives of romanticism, who were initially embodied as supporters of the high value of individual freedom - the movement for romanticism, and then the realists and naturalists, who were supporters of the realistic reflection of all aspects of life - united in new literary movements such as the movement for naturalism.

At the end of the XIX century, more than a hundred socio-literary magazines were published in Japan, which created the ground for the development of new literature. In addition to the theoretical development of the laws and regulations of this literature, translated or original works were also published in magazines.

The end of the XIX and the beginning of the XX century was a period of active integration of ideas. Japanese literature became closely acquainted with various aesthetic currents of the West and began to assimilate them. The great writer Natsume Soseki, who appeared on the literary scene at the beginning of the XX century, showed the development of the entire world literature in the form of a scheme. In it, Japanese classic literature is marked by a parallel line with European literature, while new Japanese literature is interpreted as a branch of the tree representing the entire world literature. Concepts and ideas about the autonomy of Japanese culture and the isolation of the path of development gradually disappeared.

The question of the synthesis of cultures has become one of the most important issues in the literary mind of Japan. In particular, the diversity of the Western and Eastern aesthetic views created a process of their mutually demanding each other. The traditions of both cultures, due to the peculiarities of their historical development, demanded mutual learning from each other. At the end

¹ Xodjayeve R. Qosimova G. Yapon adabiyotida zamonaviy adabiy yo'nalishlar va oqimlar. (Contemporary literary trends and trends in Japanese literature) .O'quv qo'llanma. T.2019. -P-5.

² Konrad N.I. - Yaponskaya literatura. Ot "Kodziki" do Tokutomi" (Japanese literature. From "Kojiki to Tokutomi") - M.: Nauka, 1974...-P.504

of the XIX and the beginning of the XX century, this concept was clearly manifested in Japanese literature.

Of course, there were also critics who considered the synthesis of different cultures to be a foreign and alien process for the Japanese people. However, there were many representatives of literature, such as the writer Uchimura Kanzo, who ignored the heritage of national culture and supported the creation of a new European-style literature.

Japanese literature developed in the late XIX and early XX centuries, undergoing drastic changes. In the period after the Meiji Revolution, close acquaintance with Western literature led to the emergence of various trends in Japanese literature, re-formation, and theoretical knowledge, resulting in the emergence of a unique new era of Japanese literature.

By the way, regarding the Arab countries of the Gulf, we should note that the formation of the literature of these Arab countries took place in the second half of the XX century, several decades after the development of the modern literature of Egypt, Syria, Lebanon, Iraq, and Tunisia. By the end of the XX century, it joined the world literary process and reached the world level.

The study of the literature of the Arab countries of the Gulf as a national literature that has left the traditional patterns and joined the world literary process over the past half century is of particular scientific importance, because this issue is related to the problem of the rapid development of the literature of the countries of the Arabian Peninsula. If the literary renewal in Egypt, Lebanon, Syria, and some Arab Maghrib countries began in the second half of the XIX century, in the Arab countries located on the Arabian Peninsula, this process began a century later, that is, in the second half of the XX century, and in a very short period of time, a new type of literary tradition was formed from the classical literary traditions formed in the Middle Ages. passed to modern literature.

As a result, late-developed Arabic literature in the XXI century followed a path similar to the development path of advanced Arabic literature, but they were distinguished by their own characteristics.

Such a situation led to the emergence of the "theory of rapid development" in the case of late modern literature.³

Kuwait, Bahrain, Qatar and other countries located in the Persian Gulf have taken a complex, contradictory tone in the form of a rapid transition to a new type of modern literature, rather "jumping".

We can find out the reasons for this from the fact that these Gulf Arab countries have gone through a unique, even unique, path of socio-historical development. In the first decades of the XX century, these countries lived in a backward way of life typical of the Middle Ages, and in the second half of the XX century, they experienced very sharp economic, social, and political changes. Such changes were not observed in countries such as Egypt, Syria, and Lebanon, where the literary renewal took place first.

At the same time, the accelerated development of literature in the countries located in the Persian Gulf did not go in the same direction. The formation of modern literature in Kuwait, Bahrain, Yemen, and Saudi Arabia began in the 40s and 50s of the XX century, and writers known throughout the Arab world quickly emerged and reached the level of Egyptian and Syrian literature. But in Qatar, Oman, and the United Arab Emirates, the process of literature renewal began later, that is, in the 60-70s of the XX century, and it was observed that there is a movement to quickly catch up with other Arab countries in terms of publication activity and artistic level.

If we dwell on the characteristics of the development of the literature of the countries of the Arabian Peninsula, they are not based on the Western literature, but primarily on the literature of Egypt, Syria, and Lebanon. Another unique aspect is that Arab writers did not go through the process of adapting medieval literary processes to new types of modern literary genres or did not

³ Suvorov M.N. Xudojestvennaya proza Yemena (K problema uskorenogo razvitiya literatur stran Aravii). (Artistic prose of Yemen (On the problem of accelerated development) Literature of the countries of Arabia) Avtoref.. dok... diss... Sankt-Peterburg, 2011.- P-3.

work on creating a new narrative style. They had before them the experience of Egyptian or Syrian literature in creating a new Arabic literature of 100 years. A great role was played in the formation of literary tastes by a large number of publications from Egypt, Lebanon, Syria and other parts of the Arab world, including artistic and critical works. Writers of Kuwait and Bahrain, who lived in a very difficult socio-economic environment since the 40s and 50s of the XX century, approached the ideas of the enlightened people of Egypt, Syria, and Lebanon more, because they saw the factor of their task in raising knowledge, consciousness, and moral views.

The flow of "oil money" as a result of oil production has completely changed the life of the countries of the Arabian Peninsula. The material condition of the population has increased dramatically, the opportunities to get acquainted with the world civilization have expanded through the most advanced technical means that have been brought to the country. As a result of getting to know and being influenced by various literatures, in the literature of these countries, a mixture (harmonization) of several directions was observed, from the literature of enlightenment to the modernist literature. If it took several decades for the formation and development of one direction in the literature of Egypt, Syria, and Lebanon, in the literature of Kuwait, Bahrain, and Yemen, there were situations where one direction was replaced by another direction without reaching its full formation. However, in the literature of Qatar, Oman, and the United Arab Emirates, the literature of enlightenment did not develop at all.

In general, in the countries of the Arabian Peninsula, the genres of educational literature - travelogues, historical novels, encyclopedias and philosophical works - were hardly created. Their place was taken by social-household story and social-household novel. In these works, one could sometimes sense admonition, a more romantic ("al-ittijah al-wijdania") mood. The emergence of a romantic mood in these countries was caused by sharp turns, radical changes, quietness as a result of the construction boom, and feelings of longing for the lost traditions of material life.

However, the realistic style was formed before these literatures from the styles suitable for the enlightenment or romantic spirit, because the essence of social and domestic works demanded more realistic depiction of life, events, and personalities. By this time, various forms of realism were already prevailing in the advanced literature of Egypt, Syria, and Lebanon. In the 50s and 60s of the XX century, the independence of the Arab countries of Egypt, Syria, Lebanon, Iraq, the Arab Maghreb-Tunisia, and Algeria, freed from colonialism, led to the activation of relations between the intellectuals of these countries, especially writers. The development of these relations was further helped by the fact that publishing houses, radio and television stations became the general news space.

Toha Husayn, Mahmoud Teymur, Taufiq al-Hakim, Najib Mahfuz, Yusuf Idris, Hanna Mina, Jubron Khalil Jubron, Tahir Wattor, Zunun Ayyub and other famous Arab writers were accepted as "teachers" for the writers of Al-Khalij countries, and followed them creatively, his works were carefully studied. The modern artistic prose genres that appeared in the literature of Al-Khalij - essay, story, novel, short story - were watered with the same realistic spirit.

Many writers from Kuwait and Bahrain went to study in Egypt, Lebanon, and Syria, and lived in the literary environment there.

But we would be wrong to say that the writers of "Al-Khalij" imitated Egyptian, Syrian, and Lebanese teachers, because their works had their own national character. This nationality is provided by the culture, lifestyle, social and political environment of Al-Khalij countries, and the uniqueness of the dialects used in their works.

But in the literature of these countries until the 70s, despite the development of mainly short-story writing, no significant works were created yet.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, we can say that Sulayman Shati, Abdulaziz Sari, Laila Osman, Surayya Baqsami, Ismail Fahd, Amina Shoib, Bizza al-Batini, who entered the literary field in the 70s, Kuwaiti, Bahraini Khalaf Ahmed Khalaf, Muhammad Majid, Muhammad Abdulmalik, Qatari writers such as Kulsum Jobr and Kulsum Ghanim published their first collections of short

stories. Their works quickly became known in the Arab world and were even translated into Russian, English, French and other Western languages.

Of course, it was not easy to use a realistic style in al-Khalij's literature. Even though the acquaintance of writers with realist literature samples was at a rapid pace, several internal socio-political and spiritual-cultural factors prevented the improvement of the direction of realism in these countries. First, there is the factor of limiting or banning by the state and religious control the issues that depict religion, politics, and the relationship between men and women. Secondly, the social consciousness of the authors themselves was not free from traditionalism, and the ability to think beyond the limits of the environment, community, and certain circles was not yet sufficient. Only in the middle of the 1970s, when the works of mature realism began to appear, modernist principles, influenced by Western literature, appeared in al-Khalij's literature. As a result, elements of surrealism and absurd literature appear in the stories.

In the 80s of the XX century, the literature of "Al-Khalij" improved a lot, in which works based on psychological analysis were created, which can show the inner world of a person with the image of the external environment.

Thus, we see that the modern prose developed in the Arab countries of al-Khalij in the 60s-80s of the XX century embodies the features of realism, romanticism ("al-ittijah al-vidjani") and modernism. We observe that educational literature tends to be instructive (didactic).

In conclusion, it is worth noting that when times change, both the decline and the fortune of the nation are first of all reflected in the literature. Therefore, in the process of studying literature, the spirit of that nation, its gradual development is discovered. Therefore, the importance of studying the literature of Japanese and Gulf Arab countries is incomparable.

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